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**Qualifications Frameworks:
basic elements, key recommendations and methodology**

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Chapter 1 – What is a Qualification Framework?

1.1 Different typologies of qualifications frameworks

A qualifications framework is an instrument for the development and classification of qualifications, which relates and compares qualifications using a hierarchy of levels of learning outcomes, usually of increasing complexity as a learner progresses up the levels.

There are different typologies of qualifications frameworks. The scope of frameworks may be comprehensive of all learning achievement and pathways or may be confined to a particular subsector of the education and training system – for example, initial education, adult education and training or an occupational area.

Some frameworks may have more features or dimensions e.g. credit or quality assurance criteria and a tighter structure, that is they are more prescriptive. All qualifications frameworks, however, establish a basis for improving the quality, accessibility, linkages and public or labour market recognition of qualifications within a country and internationally (adapted from OECD, 2007).

When we approach the question related to a qualifications framework, we can consider at least three main typologies:

- *Intranational frameworks*: those within specific sectors within a country;
- *National frameworks*: those that are national;
- *Transnational frameworks*: those that exist across different countries divided in two main categories:
 - Regional frameworks: among National qualifications frameworks;
 - Sectoral frameworks: limited to a particular sector.

1.2 Transnational Qualifications Frameworks

During the early years of the 21st century the increased development and implementation of National Qualifications Frameworks acted as a catalyst for more countries to follow suit, often in geographical proximity to countries with more developed NQFs. At this stage the possibilities of developing qualifications frameworks beyond the limitations of specific countries became obvious and the idea of a *Transnational Qualifications Framework* emerged.

Starting from the experience of different regions and sectors, different variations of transnational qualifications frameworks were created:

- *Regional Qualifications Frameworks*, i.e. recognition of qualifications across countries that are in geographical proximity, often, but not necessarily organised within a regional association or body (e.g. the European Qualifications Framework);
- *Transnational Sectoral Qualifications Frameworks*, i.e. recognition of qualifications across countries within or beyond the same region, but limited to a specific sector (e.g. the CARICOM TVET qualifications framework for the Caribbean Community).

One of the key purposes of Transnational qualifications frameworks, in the form of a Regional or a Sectoral one, is communicative and attempts to find commonalities between countries.

In general terms, a Transnational Qualifications Framework is an instrument for the development and classification of qualifications according to a set of criteria for levels of learning achieved between countries. Importantly though, and this differs from most NQFs, transnational qualifications frameworks usually:

- a. have less regulatory and more communicative purposes;
- b. include a wide range of sectors of education and training, if not all;
- c. have a range of national and regional policies, accords, conventions and protocols supporting them, but are not underpinned by enforceable legislation;
- d. have limited, often voluntary, institutional arrangements for governance and management.

The purpose of a Transnational framework is to be a regional/sectoral mechanism to increase:

- comparability of qualifications;
- mutual recognition of qualifications;
- credit transfer and mobility periods;
- development of regional/sectoral standards;
- reviewing and strengthening national assessment and accreditation systems;
- facilitating agreement on entrance requirements to courses and programmes;
- joint courses and programmes.

It is important to learn from lessons well-founded drawn from international practice in order to create a Transnational, Regional and a Sectoral QFs.

1.3 National Qualifications Frameworks

National qualifications frameworks (NQFs) encompass all education qualifications – or all higher education qualifications, depending on the policy of the country concerned – in an education system. They show what learners may be expected to know, understand and be able to do on the basis of a given qualification (learning outcomes) as well as how qualifications within a system articulate, that is how learners may move between qualifications in an education system.

National qualifications frameworks are developed by the competent public authorities in the country concerned. While this is ultimately the competence and responsibility of the public authorities responsible for the country's (higher) education system, however, the participation of a broad range of stakeholders – including higher education institutions, students, staff and employers – is necessary for the framework to be successful. The development of national qualifications frameworks should therefore include broad consultations.

Starting from the experience of NQFs developed within the Bologna Process, the procedure of developing national qualifications frameworks may be summarized in 10 essential steps:

1. Decision to start: Taken by the national body responsible for (higher) education (e.g. Ministry)
2. Setting the agenda: The purpose of our NQF
3. Organising the process: Identifying stakeholders; setting up a committee/WG
4. Design Profile: Level structure, Level descriptors (learning outcomes), Credit ranges
5. Consultation National discussion and acceptance of design by stakeholders
6. Approval according to national tradition by Minister/Government/legislation
7. Administrative set-up Division of tasks of implementation between HEI, QAA and other bodies
8. Implementation at institutional/programme level; Reformulation of individual study programmes to learning outcome based approach
9. Inclusion of qualifications in the NQF; Accreditation or similar
10. Self-certification of compatibility with the meta-framework concerned

Once the national qualifications framework has been developed, it should be tested and then self certified. The self certification is a process by which the competent authorities of the country concerned verify that the national qualifications framework is compatible with the overarching Framework (the Regional/Sectoral framework of reference). The self certification process should also include input from foreign experts. Once the self certification process has been completed, self certification reports should be published so other countries may access them.

It is now important to be clear about the meaning of three essential terms:

- a. Qualification
- b. Qualifications framework
- c. Qualifications system

a) By a 'qualification' we mean:

A package of standards or units judged to be worthy of formal recognition in a certificate.

This means that a qualification may be a single module or unit, if that is deemed to be worthy of formal recognition. However, it should be noted that sometimes the term 'qualification' is used to refer only to substantial programmes leading to a well-recognised and historically grounded form of certification – such as a degree – or to a form of certification associated with the capacity to undertake a defined occupational role, in some cases associated with regulations for entry to employment – i.e. a qualification to practice / meeting the requirements for practice.

b) to define a 'qualifications framework' we use the definition proposed by OECD:

A qualifications framework is an instrument for the development and classification of qualifications according to a set of criteria for levels of learning achieved. This set of criteria may be implicit in the qualifications descriptors themselves or made explicit in the form of a set of level descriptors. The scope of frameworks may be comprehensive of all learning achievement and pathways, or may be confined to a particular sector for example initial education, adult education and training or an occupational area. Some frameworks may have more design elements and a tighter structure than others; some may have a legal basis whereas others represent a consensus of views of social partners. All qualifications frameworks, however, establish a basis for improving the quality, accessibility, linkages and public or labour market recognition of qualifications within a country and internationally.

Other definitions are, of course, possible, but it is important to underline two points: first, that an NQF must have levels based on some kind of criteria and, second, that it must employ some means of ensuring that qualifications registered on the framework meet criteria related to matters such as quality and accessibility.

c) The OECD report also draws a helpful distinction between a qualifications "framework" and a qualifications "system".

Qualifications systems include all aspects of a country's activity that result in the recognition of learning. These systems include the means of developing and operationalizing national or regional policy on qualifications, institutional arrangements, quality assurance processes, assessment and awarding processes, skills recognition and other mechanisms that link education and training to the labour market and civil society...One feature of a qualifications system may be an explicit framework of qualifications.

The distinction is important because the goals that countries sometimes seek to achieve through the introduction of an NQF, often require complementary and supportive reforms in the qualifications system.

Other distinctive features of a NQFs are:

- a single system of levels for all qualifications
- qualifications based on standards or outcomes
- modular/unitised qualifications
- assessment based on explicit criteria
- a national system of credit accumulation and transfer
- a common approach to describing qualifications
- a common classification system for subjects and occupational sectors

Some people would argue that by definition an NQF must display certain characteristics e.g. being standards-based. A little background explanation is necessary here. In some countries, the terms 'outcome-based' and 'standards-based' have the same meaning, i.e. a system in which there is clear information about the outcomes of learning against which learners' performance can be judged in an assessment process. However, 'outcome-based' tends to be interpreted broadly (i.e. encompassing a variety of different ways of specifying outcomes and assessing them) while 'standards-based' is often associated with a particular approach used in New Zealand, UK National Vocational Qualifications, and many qualifications in South Africa.

It is important to be open minded about the nature of NQFs, because it is the policy goal that determines the nature and design of NQFs, not the other way around.

Chapter 2 - Lessons learned from the development of the European Qualifications Framework

2.1 The EQF in the context of the Bologna & Copenhagen processes

The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) was developed in response to requests from the member states, the social partners and other stakeholders for a common reference to increase the transparency of qualifications.

In 2002 the European ministers in charge of lifelong learning invited the European Commission in cooperation with the member states to develop a framework for the recognition of qualifications for both education and training building on the achievements of the Bologna Process and promoting a similar action in vocational training. In 2004 the ministers met in Maastricht where they stressed the priority for developing an open and flexible EQF as a common reference for both education and training. In March 2005, following work undertaken by the European Commission, the EU Heads of Government formally requested the development of an EQF. The EQF was envisaged as a framework that would bring together three significant areas of policy development: the Lisbon strategy, the Copenhagen process and the Bologna Process, initiated in 2000, 2002 and 1999 respectively.

The Lisbon strategy was intended to make the EU the most competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy in the world capable of sustainable economic growth with more and better jobs and greater social cohesion. The lifelong learning strand of the Lisbon strategy requires a challenging reform and modernisation of education systems of the member countries, with the aim that, by 2010, Europe should be the world leader in terms of the quality of its education and training systems. To achieve this, European countries need to ensure that there is continuous updating and renewal of knowledge, skills and wider competences in the workforce and that there are as few barriers as possible to accessing education and training and to building on previously acquired knowledge and skills, either within or between countries. The EQF is seen as supporting all these aims.

The Lisbon strategy is currently under revision and a new strategy for 2020 has been adopted. As part of the Lisbon strategy, enhanced cooperation in vocational education and training is being carried forward by the Copenhagen Process, which is currently focusing on quality assurance, transparency and recognition of qualifications; the development of a single Community framework for the transparency of qualifications and competences (Europass - European Commission, 2004); the development of a credit transfer system for vocational education and training (ECVET - European Commission, 2004); common criteria and principles for quality in VET (European Commission, 2004); common principles for the validation of non-formal and informal learning (European Commission, 2002); and lifelong guidance with a European dimension for learners (European Commission, 2004). All of these feature to some extent in the proposals for the EQF.

The Bologna Process, which could be said to have led the way in terms of pan-European cooperation on education matters, is concerned with the development of a European Higher Education Area (EHEA).¹ This includes the adoption of a three-cycle system of qualifications, the establishment of a credit system based on the existing European Credit Transfer System (ECTS); the promotion of the European dimension in higher education (especially in the areas of quality assurance and learner mobility); and the establishment of the framework for qualifications of the EHEA (adopted in Bergen in 2005). As indicated above, signatories to the Bologna agreement include countries which are not members of the EU, which adds an important dimension of ownership or authorisation to the negotiations that will be required to align EHEA and aspects of the Bologna process to the EQF.

¹ It should be emphasised that Bologna is not an EU initiative, instead it is coordinated by the Council of Europe which includes all the EU member states but also many non-EU countries.

Another important but separate development is the EU Directive (36/2005) on the recognition of professional qualifications that brought together several regulations on professional qualifications that are regulated at national or European level. The purpose of the Directive is to facilitate mobility for individuals holding a qualification for these regulated professions, which are de jure a license to practise. The Directive builds on a number of directives from the 70s and early 80s to harmonise the training in some key professions and leads to automatic recognition of seven professions, mainly in the health sector. It also proposes a procedure for dealing with professions that are regulated in specific member states. The Directive prescribes strict criteria, covering for example the duration, location and content of the training as a condition for recognition. As the system is based on a prescriptive approach to the training and certification requirements based on required input criteria, it only facilitates the mobility of those qualified professionals who meet the largely harmonised input criteria. This system of recognition is very different from the EQF, which aims to facilitate the comparison of levels of learning outcomes from qualifications that could have been obtained in different ways. Whereas the EQF seeks to facilitate the comparison of the results of the learning in terms of competences, the Directive establishes criteria to ensure matching training programmes. The regulated system ensures automatic recognition of individuals with the strictly corresponding professional qualifications, but does not allow partial recognition of the qualifications and skills of individuals coming from outside the matching systems. This means that skills shortages in these regulated professions cannot be filled flexibly by requalifying individuals with a relevant background through e.g. recognition of prior learning or any other shorter route than the full training programmes. The Directive is an inherited system which goes back to the seventies when the six original member states of the European Community tried to harmonise professional qualifications through harmonised training programmes. The principles promoted by the EQF are fundamentally different, and take account of the diversity of education and training systems in 27 member states and the realities of lifelong learning. They have moved away from the hard compliance of matching training programmes to the transparency and comparability of learning outcomes.

The declaration of the Ministers of Education of the European Union in Copenhagen in 2002 contained the following passage that was at the basis of the EQF:

The Ministers recommend investigating how transparency, comparability, transferability and recognition of competences and/or qualifications, between different countries and at different levels, can be promoted by developing reference levels, common principles for certification, and common measures, including a credit transfer system for vocational education and training. (Copenhagen Declaration, 30 November 2002)

This statement is quite significant as it provided a basis for both the EQF and the work on a European credit system for vocational education and training. Initially both developments were part of single initiative. A technical working group on credit transfer in VET was established in 2002. Initial work on reference levels had been commissioned by the credit transfer technical working group to the Qualifications and Curriculum Authority. Long before this work was published it started to lead a life on its own (Coles & Oates, 2004). The main message from the study which looked at different approaches to levels was that the levels should be based on learning outcomes if they were going to bridge learning from different contexts and that eight levels seemed to be the optimum number for a European framework.

The scope of the EQF work was to develop reference levels for lifelong learning and aimed to cover all forms of learning including more academic types of learning and general secondary education. Two years after the meeting in Copenhagen, ministers met again in Maastricht in 2004 to discuss progress in cooperation in vocational education and training. The ministers asked that priority should be given *'to the development of an open and flexible EQF that would cover both VET and general (secondary and higher) education and would be based on learning outcomes'* (Maastricht Communiqué, 14 December 2004). This was reconfirmed by the meeting of the Heads of Government (the Council) in March 2005.

Many experts in qualifications and qualifications systems were involved in developing the EQF. They included a large group of representatives from higher education, in particular the Bologna Follow-Up Working Group. Moreover, the expert working group included representatives from EU member states, social partners, sectors and European organisations and was led by the European Commission. The EQF descriptors for higher levels aimed to adapt the Dublin descriptors that were at the basis of the qualifications framework for the European Higher Education Area, opening them up for a wider set of qualifications. When the higher education ministers met in Bergen in May 2005 to announce the Framework of Qualifications for the European Higher Education Area, the development of the EQF was already well advanced.

2.2 The EQF consultation and the final Recommendation

The European Commission's consultation paper on the proposed EQF was published in July 2005, two months after Bergen, and went through an extensive EU-wide consultation process. The blueprint, prepared on the basis of the Expert Group's work, proposed an eight-level framework based on learning outcomes aiming to facilitate the transparency of qualifications and to support lifelong learning. The EQF was proposed as a common European reference framework which would link countries' qualifications systems together, acting as a translation device to make qualifications more readable and understandable across different countries and systems in Europe. It was presented as a meta-framework that enables different qualifications frameworks to be related to each other and subsequently to allow comparisons of individual qualifications. Such comparisons would form the basis of greater recognition and transfer of the learning outcomes (in the form of qualifications) acquired by individual citizens to facilitate the mobility of learners and workers. The paper made clear that such a meta-framework would not replace national or sectoral frameworks – indeed its viability would rest on building links with such frameworks. The EQF would be entirely voluntary, that is EU member states could choose whether or not to relate their systems to it.

The responses to the consultation demonstrated widespread support among European stakeholders for the Commission's proposal but also requested greater simplification, in particular of the reference levels. In response, the European Commission amended the original proposal, drawing on the input of experts from all the 32 countries involved as well as the European social partners. The revised text was then adopted by the Commission as a proposal on 6 September 2006. The European Parliament and the Council successfully negotiated the proposal during 2007, resulting in the EQF's formal adoption in February 2008.

The EQF was finally adopted in 2008 in a Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union of 23 April 2008 (Official Journal of the European Union, 2008/C 111). The Recommendation has a non-binding nature and thus conforms to the principle of subsidiarity. It is an example of 'soft' *acquis* of European law.

The actual EQF consists of four core elements:

- vision and objectives,
- a set of common descriptors, defined in terms of learning outcomes, and located in a structure of eight levels,
- definitions of key concepts,
- a set of common principles and procedures on quality assurance.

According to the Recommendation, the EQF has two interrelated objectives: the promotion and facilitation of regional (intra-European) mobility by increasing the transparency of qualifications throughout Europe, as well as increased portability and recognition of qualifications. Mobility is encouraged not only on a geographical level, but also between different sectors within the labour market; and to encourage implementation of lifelong learning within member states through flexible

learning pathways, promoting the recognition of non-formal and informal learning, and breaking down barriers between different sectors within education and training systems.

The Recommendation provided a condensed explanation of the purpose and mechanisms of the EQF with very concrete steps for implementation. Formally, member states were asked to reference the levels of their qualifications systems or frameworks in a transparent way to the EQF. Where appropriate, level comparison could be facilitated by developing NQFs in accordance with national legislation and practice. By 2012 new qualifications certificates should mention the EQF levels. Countries were also asked to use learning outcomes in describing qualifications and to designate national coordination points to oversee the relationship between their respective national systems and the EQF, in particular to ensure the referencing of the national system or framework to the EQF.

The key to the EQF is its eight reference levels. The EQF aims to relate different countries' national qualifications systems and frameworks together using this common European reference point. The levels span the full range of qualifications from the upper levels of compulsory schooling to the most advanced qualifications for senior professionals. The EQF, crucially, is a lifelong learning framework, so that all its eight levels encompass qualifications gained in any setting, whether general education, higher education or VET for example. They are also intended to include qualifications acquired through non-formal and informal learning and lifelong learning opportunities as well as through formal learning. The levels are said to have been decided on after analysis of evidence from published research and from the main national qualifications structures and the structures of work practice in companies in many countries.

The eight reference levels are described in terms of learning outcomes. The philosophical basis of the EQF is that Europe's education and training systems are so diverse that a shift to learning outcomes is necessary to make comparison and cooperation between countries and institutions possible. As indicated above, the Recommendation therefore requests that member states use learning outcomes when defining and describing qualifications.

2.3 The implementation of the EQF

The successful development and implementation of an EQF will require a shared understanding of key terms such as learning outcomes, qualifications, competences, and the framework itself. In using these terms, the 2005 consultation paper drew on the work of the OECD, the ETF, Cedefop and other international organisations and attempts to take developments under both the Bologna and Copenhagen processes into account, making adjustments to meet the specific context of the European meta-framework. It is not always clear, however, how far the issues associated with these terms are terminological and how far they are deeper, related more to fundamental beliefs about the processes which underlay the terms. For example, the Recommendation defines qualifications as *'formal outcomes of an assessment or validation process which is obtained when a competent body determines that an individual learning outcome is to a given standard'* and states clearly that the details of specific qualifications will not be described by the EQF, for which instead the national qualifications systems are the appropriate reference. But it does state that the EQF should enable international sectoral organisations to relate their qualifications systems to a common European reference point and thus show the relationship between international sectoral qualifications and national qualifications systems.

In order to facilitate the national coordination of referencing processes, the 2005 consultation paper had also pointed out that all current agencies for making comparisons between qualifications – networks such as the European Network of National Information Centres (ENIC), the National Academic Recognition Information Centres (NARIC), the national reference points for vocational qualifications, and the National Europass Centres – will need to be involved. The Recommendation itself formally takes account of Europass. These are examples of an area where the EQF seems to prompt, if not create, issues about existing structures and the need for structural changes in the

wake of the EQF. As stated above, the Recommendation asks member states to designate national coordination points in order to support and guide the relationship between the national qualifications systems and the EQF. One of their tasks is to promote the participation of all relevant stakeholders including higher education and vocational education and training institutions, social partners, sectors, and experts in the comparison and use of qualifications at the European level.

The European Commission's view seems to be that the development of a single NQF, based on learning outcomes, and overseen by a national authority (whether agency or ministry) is the ideal approach to support national linking to the EQF. In this and other ways, it seems unlikely that the EQF will not require or result in some degree of convergence between national and (possibly to a lesser extent) sectoral systems and this raises two questions: how far down the national or sectoral systems will it be necessary to pursue measures of commonality and will the EQF turn out to be an instrument of change, in the control of those who choose to use it, or an agent for change, of its very nature requiring specific kinds of change.

While the EQF aims to make systems throughout Europe more comparable, there is strong resistance to uniformity. However, convergence is likely to take place. On the one hand, maintaining longstanding national traditions in education and training, for example, the dual model approach in Germany, Denmark and Austria, is seen as essential in responding to national challenges. On the other hand, in higher education within the Bologna Process some form of harmonisation of higher education models has been promoted. Some degree of convergence in VET to the apprenticeship model seems to be gaining ground as well. International pressure for uniformity in European and international certificates and the pressure towards more compatible qualifications systems within NQFs are all factors that cannot be disregarded.

However, there is a clear distinction between the Bologna Process and the EQF here. Although not mentioned explicitly in the official declarations, in Bologna circles the word harmonisation is frequently used. The official Bologna website (www.ehea.info) mentions that provisions of the Bologna Declaration were set as measures of a voluntary harmonisation process. The introduction of common degree structures (the three-cycle degree system) has actually changed higher education provision in most of the 48 countries that participate in the Bologna Process. Here, a degree of harmonisation is evident.

The EQF, on the other hand, is not an instrument for harmonising qualifications or parts of qualifications systems but is intended to function as a type of translation device to make relationships between qualifications and different systems clearer. The articles on education and vocational training on the EU's governing treaty explicitly exclude any harmonisation of the laws and regulations of the member states. But this does not mean that the EQF could not lead to a convergence of systems, as a number of countries now seem to be adopting eight levels for their national frameworks. But behind these levels an enormous diversity of systems and qualifications continues to exist.

The level descriptors are the core of the EQF. They are stated in terms of learning outcomes under three headings: knowledge, skills, and wider competences described in terms of responsibility and autonomy. Learning outcomes are defined in Annex 1 of the Recommendation as *'the statements of what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to do on completion of a learning process which are defined in terms of knowledge, skills and competence'*. These are set out at eight levels, with changes in the levels reflecting increased ability to deal with complexity, unpredictability and change.

The development of the EQF as a meta-framework is a new enterprise and raises a number of issues as it breaks new ground. An important example here is the development of the EQF descriptors and levels which represents a compromise between 27 countries and is not necessarily a product of purely technical procedures; this notion of a 'social construction' – that is, agreed between partners – which extends far beyond the technical has in recent years proven to be a

fundamental conceptual shift that has directly contributed to the successful development and implementation of qualifications frameworks internationally. This conclusion is well formulated by Markowitsch and Luomi-Messerer when discussing the development and interpretation of descriptors of the EQF: *'The EQF is very much a political/pragmatic tool and not a scientific/empirical tool.'*

The reference points have been designed and written to support the work of policy-makers and experts at national and sectoral levels and to make comparisons and cooperation easier to achieve and manage. It is intended that national and sectoral bodies will add amplification and exemplification to the EQF that will make it easier for national and sectoral experts to use the levels with their own qualifications. There is no intention that all qualifications should equally match all three types of outcome, and where they do, it is acknowledged that they may relate to different types of outcome at different levels. Thus the reference table of EQF outcomes will have to be used to achieve a 'best fit' match of national and sectoral qualifications to a level. According to the EQF Advisory Group note (European Commission, 2010), 'best fit' is a decision that is based on collective professional judgments of stakeholders. The best-fit principle (i.e. the referencing to the level that best matches the qualification) is thought to be a feasible method for classification. Precisely because education and training tracks impart knowledge, skills and competence to varying degrees and therefore qualifications cannot always be characterised unambiguously with one set of descriptors, experts see the best-fit principle as a welcome approach to referencing. On the other hand, the process of 'best fit' includes deciding on the weighting given to the technical and social dimensions in the final referencing decision. One of the main technical issues here is how to compare fairly distinct domains of learning outcomes used by different countries. In the case of the English and Northern Irish report (QF, 2009) the social dimension was given a strong weighting in matching level 4 of the national framework to the EQF.

Quality assurance forms the basis for mutual trust within the EQF and emphasis is placed on simplicity through the development of guidelines that support quality assurance development within NQFs. Quality assurance is also part of the referencing criteria. The Recommendation provides a set of common principles for quality assurance in higher education and vocational education and training.

2.4 Quality assurance aspects and the governance of the EQF

The risk of a potential over-dependence of the EQF on national quality assurance processes is further mitigated through several pan-European arrangements, such as the European Quality Assurance Framework for VET (EQA VET), the work of Cedefop on the examination of EU experiences on the relationship between quality assurance and VET certification (Cedefop, 2009) and other exchange experiences. A sub-group of the EQF Advisory Group also focuses on the relationships between national and regional quality assurance processes. The short-term integration of national and regional (trans-Europe) processes is however not foreseen.

Implementation of the EQF is based on an open method of coordination, which includes three key implementation structures.

a. The *EQF Advisory Group* is the main coordination body that oversees the implementation of the EQF and provides coherence to the various processes. It consists of representatives from the member states, candidate countries, and countries from the European Economic Area outside the EU, the Council of Europe (which oversees the Bologna Process), European social partners and various other stakeholders, such as chambers of commerce and industry, public employment services, and the voluntary sector. The Advisory Group meets between three to four times per year and has been responsible for the development of guidelines and procedures to be followed by member states when referencing their education levels in various attempts to develop mutual trust between them.

b. *National coordination points (NCPs)* are responsible for more practical issues and ensure that country-specific issues are raised. In particular the tasks of the NCPs include: (i) referencing levels of qualifications within national qualifications systems to the EQF levels; (ii) ensuring that a transparent methodology is used to reference national qualifications levels to the EQF; (iii) providing access to information and guidance to stakeholders on how national qualifications relate to the EQF through national qualifications systems; and (iv) promoting the participation of all relevant stakeholders. To date these coordination points have been funded by the countries, but there has been a recent shift (following the global economic crisis) to provide specific funding in this area from 2010. Strong links exist between country representatives who sit on the Advisory Group and the EQF national coordination points. In 2010 the first network meetings of NCPs took place.

c. *Support/working groups* are thematically based. Examples include sector qualifications, resources for the EQF, website development, quality assurance, and the learning outcomes approach. The support groups are very active and ensure systematic exchange of experiences within the EQF environment. For example, the work of the group on learning outcomes, involving representatives from more than 20 European countries, culminated in the preparation of European guidelines for validating non-formal and informal learning (Cedefop, 2009). This group has also been a peer learning forum for exchanging experience on the development of NQFs in the countries that participate in the EQF process.

The role of the European Commission is central to the EQF implementation process as it is responsible for implementation at the European level; the Commission takes political initiatives on the transnational level, while the education and training function remains national. Despite the recognition of the importance of the Commission and other EU agencies, capacity and resources have remained limited according to stakeholders, and used mainly to pay contractors for specific projects, support to the working groups, and increasingly, to improve communication in the qualifications community. A small team in the Directorate General for Education and Culture coordinates the implementation of the EQF, supported by a locally-based expert from Cedefop.

The coordinating role of the EQF Advisory Group is seen as equally important, the more so because the EQF is a voluntary instrument that remains dependent on member states and other stakeholders' willingness to implement it. The need for a semi-autonomous regional agency is not high on the agenda within the EU as education and training is regarded as a national competence. The European Commission's services and the EQF Advisory Group are regarded as sufficient governance structures. Continuity of key staff is noted as an important factor for the relatively quick development of the EQF to date, although it is also noted that continuity and consistency has to be balanced with new thinking. The improvement of communication about qualifications and competences is increasingly being prioritised within the EQF context. The work of the EU bodies in particular is viewed as important. Examples include the support from agencies such as Cedefop and the ETF, the availability of resources for testing and piloting mainly through the Leonardo da Vinci programme, and engaging with external experts. National coordinating mechanisms (like national qualifications agencies) are viewed as essential by the European Commission and member states.

In a wider context, the EQF implementation is also supported by important Community instruments for mobility and innovation in VET – the Leonardo da Vinci programme and the European Social Fund. It is also supported by stakeholders' platforms such as the Directors General for Vocational Training (DGVT) and the Advisory Committee for Vocational Training, and other forums of European social dialogue.

Today the EQF represents an important shift towards outcomes-based qualifications, through a focus on transparency within a diverse context. Cooperation takes place on the basis of recognised differences and not in an attempt to harmonise national systems. Referencing of the 27

member states NQFs against the EQF has been prioritised, and most countries indicate that they plan to have completed the necessary processes by the end of 2011.

2.5 Influences and impact of the EQF

The learning outcome approach is seen as essential to the EQF. Even so, there are also some cautionary notes as the learning outcomes used to describe some qualifications are criticised for not sufficiently connecting to the labour market and the needs of employers; this issue has been identified as a key challenge by the European Commission and attempts are underway to connect referencing at national level with the labour market and employers. The need to go beyond learning outcomes, and also address curricula, teaching and assessment is often noted. Here also, the inclusion of learning outcomes in the Bologna higher education process has laid an important foundation for the EQF process.

Recent studies have shown that qualifications are changing in form but not necessarily in function, and as a result, a huge change in recognition of qualifications nationally or internationally is not expected (see ILO, 2010; and Cedefop, 2009). Even so there is no doubt that learning outcomes are clearly having an impact on the way in which the recognition of qualifications is understood and are contributing directly to the development of new methodologies for recognition. The extent to which the learning outcomes approach contributes to recognition of qualifications in practice is however less certain at this stage of the EQF's development.

The relationship between the EQF and the Bologna higher education framework is acknowledged as critically important. The fact that EU member states are now developing comprehensive NQFs (i.e. which include higher education, VET and other training sectors) is regarded as a direct result of the coordination between the EQF and the Bologna Process, which pioneered development in the higher education sector. The Bologna Process has been an important point of inspiration for the EQF. In particular the Dublin descriptors developed for the three cycles of higher education defined by Bologna were adapted to fit within levels 5 to 8 of the EQF, the EQF descriptors taking account additionally of skills and autonomy alongside the more knowledge-oriented focus of the Dublin descriptors.

Nevertheless, the main criticism against the EQF is that it does not sufficiently tackle the barriers between VET and higher education. The extent to which the EQF (and learning outcomes) may encourage modularisation and the development of part qualifications is also of concern to some stakeholders. While it is not evident that the EQF is hindered in its implementation by the varying levels of application of quality assurance systems in member states, it is recognised that some member states still have much to do in developing robust national quality assurance systems.

The development and establishment of the EQF is a condition for the introduction of the credit accumulation and transfer scheme in all vocational qualifications across the EU, known as the European Credit System for Vocational Education and Training (ECVET). It is also an important driver for using learning outcomes for defining and describing qualifications. In this regard, qualification frameworks in general are criticised by some actors for having 'taken the pedagogy out of education and training'. In some contexts this influence is welcomed and seen as contributing to the opening of access and improvement of parity of esteem; this view is however severely contested. The assumption that much of the experience gained in the process of building NQFs can be translated to transnational qualifications frameworks, particularly regional qualifications frameworks such as the EQF, is questioned as it is argued that such broader applicability has not been verified in practice.

There is an issue about unintended and potentially negative impacts of the EQF. These presumed effects are varied but include the potential devaluing of traditional offerings of vocational education, additional bureaucracy, dangers in adapting to an extreme form of outcomes (that overlook teaching inputs and learning conditions), and ensuring that a critical mass of countries remains

involved. The potential convergence of education and training systems, as mentioned above, may undermine the positive diversity of education systems – a hidden kind of harmonisation is feared.

Chapter 3 - How to develop a Qualifications Framework

3.1 Preliminary elements to consider

As we already described, a Qualifications Framework - considering all the typologies already presented - is an instrument for the development, classification and recognition of skills, knowledge and competencies along a continuum of agreed levels. It is a way of structuring existing and new qualifications, which are defined by learning outcomes, i.e. clear statements of what the learner must know or be able to do whether learned in a classroom, on-the-job, or less formally. The Qualifications Framework indicates the comparability of different qualifications and how one can progress from one level to another, within and across occupations or industrial sectors (and even across vocational and academic fields if the NQF is designed to include both vocational and academic qualifications in a single framework).

The scope of frameworks may be comprehensive of all learning achievement and pathways or may be confined to a particular sector for example initial education, adult education and training or an occupational area. Some frameworks may have more design elements and a tighter structure than others; some may have a legal basis whereas others represent a consensus of views of social partners. All qualifications frameworks, however, provide a basis for improving the quality, accessibility, linkages and public or labour market recognition of qualifications within a country and internationally. The variation in the definition of QFs is often a source of confusion.

(i) The important point is that the nature and design of the QF should be based on the goals that policy makers and decision makers seek to achieve by introducing a QF.

The value of a QF, or a NQF, lies in its potential to contribute to policy goals such as lifelong learning, recognition of skills, or improving the quality of education and training. Therefore its design should relate to the goals which it is intended to support and to the context in which it will operate. It is unhelpful to think of the NQF as an entity with fixed or universal characteristics – other than the need to establish a set of levels and criteria for registering and allocating qualifications to these levels.

(ii) The most effective approach to building a QF is to start with clear policy aims, rather than with a set idea about the particular characteristics it should have.

A NQF, or a Sectoral one, can help to address a number of the skills challenges; however, a framework is not a quick solution to the many skills challenges faced by a country or a sector. Without clear objectives and an understanding of how a QF can best be developed, implementation can be a lengthy and costly endeavour.

(iii) Conducting a preliminary analysis to be clear about rationales for the development of a QF is vital.

It should enable policy makers to get beyond general QF rhetoric and focus on the specific needs of the country or sector and lay the foundation for a needs-led approach to NQF design and implementation. It is important to be sure that there is a real problem or need to be addressed. Obviously, it is highly counter-productive to impose 'solutions' where a problem does not exist. It is also important to be clear about priorities, especially where there are significant resource constraints. For example, revising all VET qualifications to create a fully outcome-based modular system is an expensive undertaking and the benefits may not immediately justify the investment. It may suggest focusing efforts on one sector of education and training rather than a comprehensive NQF which includes all sectors of education and training. The final goal may be to build a comprehensive NQF, but it does not need to be a one-stage process.

(iv) The approach to QF construction should also be decided on the basis of fit-for-purpose.

The most important thing is to develop genuine support and trust for the NQF among stakeholders. Employers' and workers' organizations have a key role to play in this process.

(v) A National Qualifications Framework or a Sectoral Qualifications Framework is only a framework and it is based on 'qualifications'.

The key to successful QF implementation is to develop a broad strategy that takes account of all factors influencing success. These include: policy coherence across different ministries; an enabling funding regime; support to education and training institutions including the development of learning materials and professional development.

As for the governance and management of the NQF, it is normal international practice for the management of the NQF to be assigned to an apex body, such as a national qualifications authority, that is independent of the government but accountable to it.

(vi) This is also valid during the development of a Regional or a Sectoral QF: it is fundamental to indicate a supranational apex body within the specific region or sector concerned.

Two key issues of governance are: co-ordination of policy across government ministries and ensuring adequate involvement of stakeholders. It is recommended, however, that one body (e.g. ministry) be chosen to take the lead role so as to create an effective internal policy coordination mechanism.

(vii) The first essential element of QF development is to develop a set of 'levels' of learning to be achieved (i.e. learning outcomes, competencies, functions, etc.) and assign qualifications to the levels.

The starting point in deciding on the number of levels is the current understanding among stakeholders about key qualifications and their relationship to each other. A QF is unlikely to be accepted or even understood by citizens, stakeholders and learners if it does not correspond to 'common sense' within a certain sector.

(viii) Learning outcomes, competencies, functions or any other useful elements are used to create different levels and they do not change the nature of the framework that is composed by different qualifications and only 'based' on those elements: it is a 'qualifications framework', not a 'learning outcomes framework'.

The number of levels in a QF varies and depends to the real situation and the real organisation of different systems and sectors.

(ix) The second essential element of any QF is quality assurance.

This is vital if stakeholders within a country, a sector and the international community are to have confidence in the QF. Three important measures of quality assurance are:

- validation of qualifications and/or standards;
- accreditation and audit of education and training institutions;
- quality assurance of assessment leading to the award of qualifications.

The process of developing a framework of qualifications must take into account the need to foster trust among the various stakeholders so that they can have confidence in the integrity of the resultant framework.

(x) It is vital to identify the national and international stakeholders and advance consensus-building mechanisms in framework development through dialogue.

An important way to build trust and acceptance is to ensure that any top-down approach is fused with a bottom-up process. It is possible to design different ways to consult but, in general, the approach should be as transparent as possible.

3.2 Categorisation of the stages of Regional / Sectoral QF development

Qualifications frameworks can be categorised according to various stages of development. While such a categorisation is always subjective and a simplification of reality, the categorisation does at least offer a lens through which to compare different qualifications frameworks with each other.

The following table describes the categorisation of the stages of Regional and Sectoral qualifications frameworks development. Importantly the stages are not presented as mutually exclusive as it may be possible that a qualifications framework can be at more than one stage at the same time.

Stage	Description	Types of evidence
Exploration / Orientation	Growing awareness and interest in a Regional / Sectoral qualifications framework on a regional / sectoral level	Inclusion of the vision of a qualifications framework in regional / sectoral / international documents (such as strategic plans)
	Understanding of the value of a Regional / Sectoral qualifications framework for cross-border provisioning	
	Discussions on a Regional / Sectoral qualifications framework in regional / sectoral forums	
Conceptual	Decision in principle in favour of a Regional / Sectoral qualifications framework	Regional / Sectoral qualifications framework concept and discussion document(s) developed
	Expectations discussed	
	Focus is on legislation and/or regional / sectoral consensus	
	Roles of key stakeholders	Regional / international / sectoral steering group/committee established
	Resourcing	
	Compromises take place	
Testing	Pilot projects initiated (often sector specific)	Sectoral projects
	Some qualifications registered on the qualifications framework	Initial qualifications registered on qualifications framework

Implementation	Regional / international / sectoral body responsible to oversee the qualifications framework established (or identified if it is an existing body)	Regional / international / sectoral body
	Regional or sectoral legislation / policy / protocol finalised/agreed	Legislation
	Regional / sectoral funding secured	Funding
Review	Re-conceptualisation	Formal review process
	Review of impact and progress	Review report
	Re-design	

3.3 Steps of qualifications framework development

There is no single best approach to QF development: it depends on the typology of the framework (national, regional, sectoral). However, thanks to international and national experiences, it is possible to identify a linear process to help decision makers think through the issues in a structured way. In reality, of course, the process is not a simple linear one. QF development tends to be iterative, i.e. decisions made or problems arising at particular stages can necessitate reviewing decisions or views reached at an earlier stage.

Step 1 - What are the goals you want to achieve through developing a QF?

The crucial first step in QF policy formation is being clear about the purposes and goals that the QF is expected to contribute to achieving. These vary across different countries, regions and sectors.

It is important to be sure that there is a real problem or need to be addressed and to be clear whether the problem affects all sectors of education and training or just one and in which context (one, some or all countries).

There are different main sets of reasons for developing a QF:

a) Promoting lifelong learning:

- improving understanding of learning routes and qualifications and how they relate to each other;
- improving access to education and training opportunities;
- creating incentives for participation in education and training;
- making progression routes easier and clearer;
- improving learner and career mobility.

b) Improving quality assurance and recognition:

- increasing and improving credit transfer between qualifications;
- ensuring that education and training standards are defined by agreed learning outcomes and applied consistently;

- ensuring that education and training providers meet certain quality standards;
- securing international recognition for national qualifications .

Conducting a preliminary and clear analysis on real problems and needs will create a working rationale for the development of a QF.

It should enable decision makers to get beyond general QF rhetoric and focus on the specific needs of their country or sector. It may lead to the identification of the need for further research. It may lead to concentration on one or two objectives that are of paramount importance. It may suggest focussing efforts on one sector of education and training rather than another. Above all, it should lay the foundation for a needs-led approach to QF design and implementation.

Step 2 - Which sector of education and training you want to include in the QF?

There are three main sectors of education and training with interests in a QF: secondary schools, vocational education and training (VET) including work-based learning and higher education.

The boundaries between these sectors vary across countries and are difficult to define. In some countries, the secondary school sector includes vocational schools; in others, VET is delivered almost entirely through post-secondary institutions. Some countries regard aspects of VET (e.g. higher technician level qualifications) as part of the higher education sector, others would not, some countries make a clear distinction between formal and informal VET, others regard these types of VET as a single sector.

In the case of Regional and Sectoral QFs it is important to consider that each country has a specific educational and training system influenced by different legislative and cultural elements.

An educational system alike to another does not exist: the nature and the 'value' of qualifications that exist in each national context and that are referred to the same educational sector, as well as the nature and the status of education and training providers are very different. Also the way to get a qualification is influenced by the national legislation (formal programmes, recognition of prior learning

A general and clear picture of each national education and training system of the sector concerned is fundamental to create a QF and to give the possibility to develop future NQFs.

Step 3 - How should the QF be governed and managed?

At this stage, it is important to consider how the QF will be governed and managed. The governance role is the setting of strategic direction and determination of policy. This will normally be carried out by a Board, although the nature of the arrangements for governance will depend on the organisational structure of the QF. The management role is the implementation of agreed policy, carried out by executive officers in the main organisations with responsibilities for the QF. The officers will be accountable to the governing Board.

It is normal international practice for the management of the QF to be assigned to an apex body, such as a national qualifications authority for NQFs or international organisations for RQFs or SQFs.

There are two key issues of governance:

- co-ordination of policy across government ministries or different countries;
- ensuring adequate involvement of stakeholders at national and international level.

Starting on the assumption that a QF is a process and not a fixed instrument, for a QF to operate effectively, some sets of functions must be carried out:

- management of the framework;
- standards and qualifications development;
- developing, implementing and reviewing QF procedures;
- consulting with stakeholders on QF development and implementation;
- disseminating public information and advice on the NQF.

Step 4 - How should a system of levels be developed?

In respect of many aspects of QF design and implementation, policy and decision makers do not require a detailed grasp of the technicalities involved; it is sufficient to be clear about the principles. The development of the QF levels may be something of an exception to this rule, because of the importance and sensitivity of some of the issues at stake.

Assigning qualifications to levels involves judgements about the relative 'worth' or 'value' of different qualifications. It is quite normal for the representatives of academic and vocational education to hold different views on these matters and to defend such views vigorously. The process leading to agreement on levels may therefore need to be managed skilfully.

Where qualification levels are associated with national regulations or agreements on pay and promotion, the definition of these levels will be particularly sensitive.

In addition, the levels system adopted is a key aspect of defining the relationships and equivalences between the qualifications of one country and those in the rest of the world. It may therefore assume a high political significance.

It is important that stakeholders understand that qualifications at the same level are deemed to be equivalent in certain respects, and not the same.

Qualifications at the same level may be quite different in size and scope and have quite different purposes. One may prepare learners for study of an academic subject at a higher level; another may indicate competence in an occupation. Equivalence means that the qualifications concerned match certain criteria for a particular level as set out in level descriptors. However, as you will see below, level descriptors may consist of a number of types of outcome, such as knowledge, skills, communicative competence etc. Different types of qualification do not necessarily place an equal emphasis on each of the outcomes. For example, one may be relatively knowledge-oriented and another relatively skills-oriented. Nevertheless, looking at the level descriptor overall, it may be deemed to be broadly equivalent in terms of progression – i.e. requiring a similar level of capability for entry and offering similar capabilities for progression to employment or for further education and training. Specific judgments about entry or progression will, of course, also have to take account of the nature of the areas of skill and knowledge acquired by the learner. Returning to the notion of size, it should be noted that qualifications at the same level may require quite different periods of learning. Measuring and recognising the size or weight of learning is generally achieved through credit systems.

The stages in developing the system of levels are normally as follows:

- decide on the scope of the framework;
- determine the number of levels;
- develop level descriptors;
- develop practical guidance on any processes in which the descriptors are central.

The number of levels in a QF varies.

The starting point in deciding on the number of levels is the current understanding among stakeholders about key qualifications and their relationship to each other – what might be called 'the relativities' in the national system or among national systems involved.

A QF is unlikely to be accepted or even understood by citizens if it does not correspond to 'common sense', certainly in respect of the most significant qualifications.

In almost all countries, there will be a clear progression route from lower secondary qualifications (typically at the end of compulsory schooling) to upper secondary school qualifications and on to higher education qualifications. It may also be clear how a learner progresses from lower secondary qualifications into the VET qualifications structure. These key qualifications and the relationship between them are important benchmarks that will help stakeholders to relate to and understand the system of levels being proposed.

Over the last two decades there have been examples of frameworks with as many as twelve or as few as five levels, but most frameworks today seem to have around eight or ten levels.

The table below shows the eight levels that are common to most NQFs. It also takes account of the eight levels adopted by for the European Qualifications Framework.

Level	Examples of qualifications and related competences
8	Doctoral degree; Senior Manager VQ - jobs requiring the knowledge, creativity and leadership skills to deal with complex and unpredictable situations
7	Masters degree; Specialist Professional Qualifications; Senior Manager VQ - specialist knowledge-based professional work; high-level management responsibilities
6	Bachelors degree/ Honours degree; Professional Qualifications; Middle Manager VQ - knowledge-based professional work; management responsibilities
5	Higher Education Certificate and Diploma; Technician/Specialist VQ; Para-professional Qualification; Advanced Vocational Qualification – highly skilled employment; management training
4	Senior School Exit Qualification; Advanced Craft VQ; Supervisory VQ - fully skilled employment; independent operative; supervisory responsibilities
3	Junior School Exit Qualification; Intermediate VQ – skilled / semi-skilled employment
2	Basic VQ - skills required to function in the workplace
1	Literacy and Numeracy Qualification - skills required to enter the workplace and undertake vocational training

Each country and also each sector should adopt the number of levels that makes most sense in relation to its own education and training system and policy goals.

Taking into account the example of the European Qualifications Framework, Member countries may have varying numbers of levels for their NQFs, but will use the EQF reference levels as a common point of comparison.

Step 5 - Must QFs be based on outcomes?

The question is sometimes asked: must QFs be based on outcomes? The answer is that it depends what you mean by 'outcomes'. In the consultation paper on an EQF, the European Commission defines learning outcomes as:

The set of knowledge, skills and/or competences an individual has acquired and/or is able to demonstrate after completion of a learning process. Learning outcomes are statements of what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to do at the end of a period of learning.

The consultation document goes on:

Learning outcomes can be formulated for a number of purposes; in relation to individual courses, units, modules and programmes. They may furthermore be used by national authorities to define entire qualifications – sometimes structured within or linked to qualifications frameworks and systems. International bodies may, finally, use learning outcomes for the purposes of transparency, comparability, credit transfer and recognition.

Following these definitions, it would be very difficult, if not impossible, to have a QF that was not outcome-based. Without some explicit statements about the general outcomes of qualifications, it would be hard to compare different types of qualifications or to decide how to place new qualifications on different NQFs.

It is not absolutely essential for the qualifications themselves to be defined in terms of learning outcomes. However, there are many reasons why it is valuable to have the contents of the framework described in at least broad outcome terms.

In some sectors different level descriptors that are useful to create QF levels already exist: our attention have to be done on level descriptors, a fundamental part of any QF, but the contents of those could be very different.

It is important to be aware of the purposes of level descriptors and their limitations. Level descriptors have two main purposes.

a. They make explicit the tacit understandings of providers and stakeholders about the nature of qualification levels and educational progression.

The process of developing level descriptors compels those engaged in it to make clear statements about the characteristics and outcomes of qualifications and how qualifications at adjacent levels differ from each other. This can often highlight ambiguities and inconsistencies and lead to clearer and better-grounded understandings.

b. They provide a means of making comparisons across different types of qualification.

This is important in the development of progression routes and vital in the implementation of credit transfer systems.

There is more than one dimension of 'level'. Some qualifications are more concerned with development of knowledge; others with skills or personal and professional competences. The use of broadly defined level descriptors provides the basis for agreeing that qualifications belong at the same level notwithstanding different relative emphases on knowledge, skills etc. Note: it is generally the case in existing frameworks that qualifications do not have to meet all aspects of a level descriptor to be deemed to meet the level requirements.

Step 6 - How should the QF be quality assured?

One of the essential element of a QF is quality assurance. If stakeholders within the country and the international community are to have confidence in the QF, there needs to be some appropriate procedures for ensuring that QF qualifications are fit for purpose and well-designed, that programmes leading to these qualifications are being delivered by competent providers and that assessment leading to the award of the qualifications can be trusted.

Thus, there are three important elements of quality assurance: validation of qualifications and/or standards; accreditation and audit of education and training institutions; and quality assurance of assessment leading to the award of qualifications.

All frameworks require providers to be recognised in some way, although the extent to which there are formal processes varies.

Quality assurance systems are set up to ensure improvement and accountability of education and training. They aim at increasing the effectiveness and transparency of provision at all levels and thereby promoting mutual trust, recognition and mobility, within and across countries.

A culture of quality improvement is only created when there is a sense of responsibility for quality at grass roots level. The aim of policy makers should be to encourage institutions and countries to

take responsibility for quality in collaboration with the stakeholders.

The different sectors of education and training have traditionally adopted different approaches to quality assurance. It is recommended therefore that the approach should be to agree the general principles of quality assurance, then allow each sector to develop quality assurance procedures based on these principles but reflecting the needs and traditions of the sector. The body managing the QF should avoid creating elaborate and bureaucratic quality assurance machinery.

QF quality assurance should focus on the essentials – sometimes 'less is more'.

Step 7 - How should consultation processes be conducted?

The process of developing a framework of qualifications must take into account the need to foster trust among the various stakeholders so that they can have confidence in the integrity of the resultant framework. It is vital to identify the stakeholders and advance consensus-building mechanisms in framework development. An important way to build trust and acceptance is to ensure that any top-down approach is fused with a bottom-up process. It is possible to design different ways to consult but in general, the approach should be as transparent as possible. As well as positively targeting some more obvious stakeholders to request their participation, it is also useful to invite open public participation. Even if most of the effective contributions come from core stakeholders, the legitimacy is enhanced by public processes. One can also find helpful ideas from unexpected places.

The stakeholders may include:

- learners/students;
- government departments;
- appropriate government agencies including those responsible for employment, economic development, competition and immigration;
- providers of education and training;
- awarding bodies and quality assurance agencies;
- teachers and trainers staff associations;
- employers' and workers' organizations, or more broadly representatives of employers and workers;
- community and voluntary organisations;
- professional bodies;
- academic researchers working on education and labour force policy questions;
- educators of teachers and trainers;

Any person or organisation who contributes via the open consultation process should be considered to have self-identified as a stakeholder. Some stakeholders are more difficult to access than others. They may not have a representative organisation or there may be more than one such organisation, perhaps in competition with each other. Those who do have representative structures may need appropriate time to consult in turn with their membership. The value of the views of stakeholder organisations to consensus development depends on the extent to which they are indeed representative. It also depends on how much they are aware about how their members perceive the usefulness of the framework.

Consensus-building mechanisms in the development of QFs may include a number of measures such as:

- broad composition of any formal body and its executive staff;
- a publicly advertised consultation phase;
- publication of papers and submissions on the internet;
- international research and consultation;
- formal survey work with learners and employers;

- a broadly-based consultative group that meets regularly to produce extensive, supporting documentation;
- an open approach by all to questioning the purposes of qualifications and standards;
- sector meetings (e.g., to consider employment, community, and voluntary sector perspectives);
- bilateral meetings with stakeholder organisations;
- the securing of on-going political support for the initiative;
- consultation outside each country and at international level, particularly with jurisdictions where there is high labour and/or learner mobility;
- participation in international organisations and meetings.

While it is useful to have an indicative timeline and work-plan, it is also important to be flexible.

If consultation reveals profound tensions, it is important to attempt to resolve these as they arise, rather than bury them to re-emerge later. If necessary the time for consultation should be extended. The lead body should take the role of facilitating direct dialogue among stakeholders rather than mediating stakeholders' views to each other. Let each group hear or read each other's hopes and fears and respond to these directly rather than project them all onto some framework development expert group.

At the same time it is important that consultation should not be allowed to become a delaying mechanism. One tactic to avoid this is to differentiate stages of the development and 'bank' consensus as it is achieved. These stages might include initial agreement on broad principles and responsibilities, followed by policies and criteria for the framework, followed by technical details, followed by an implementation plan, followed by a communications plan. When agreement has been reached on a stage, publish the outcome and refer to it explicitly in the work that follows. Some stakeholders will find it difficult to engage with all stages; this is only to be expected. Some may have broad policy interest and little concern for details. Some others may be less interested in the abstract principles or technical details but participate more enthusiastically when they see the prospect of implementation. Information should be provided in a way that stakeholders can identify whether the particular stage is one on which they have a contribution to make.

As a principle, any framework will have to be subject to possible review and revision and stakeholders will want reassurance that this is the case.

At the same time, it needs to be acknowledged that a change can be expensive and should not be undertaken lightly. Some features of frameworks are more difficult to change than others. A change, which has a knock-on effect on all qualifications in the framework such as changing levels or level descriptors, will have implications right down to curricular development and assessment.

The point here is that any change is possible but that it is essential to understand the implications of future change. Therefore, certain key decisions such as on levels should be made carefully, in the knowledge that subsequent change could be difficult and expensive.

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